

The Influence of The Role of Parents on Children's Social Independence in The Cempaka Cluster Kindergarten, Central Banjarmasin District

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ABSTRACT

At the Gugus Cempaka Kindergarten, children Not yet show attitude independent at school . This is caused children too spoiled by parents them . Parent get used to child For independent , get what are they want , so you can Study responsible answer , esp For self yourself . Research objective : influence role to independence social children at Gugus Cempaka Kindergarten, Central Banjarmasin. Study This use approach quantitative with explanatory method , namely because consequence . Population study This totaling 360 with a sample of 189 people used technique sample proportional . Study This use questionnaire , analysis regression , and path analysis . The result show influence parental role _ to independence social children in the Cempaka Cluster Kindergarten, Central Banjarmasin District, is 15% , while factor other influence by 85% .

INTRODUCTION

Independence is an important part of the human personality that is interrelated with other aspects. It needs to be taught to children from an early age so as not to hinder their development. Independence does not develop by itself, but requires encouragement and help from others. According to Masrun et al (1986), independence is a trait that allows someone to act freely, do something on their own encouragement, pursue achievement, be full of confidence, and have the desire to do something without the help of others. Independence also involves the ability to overcome problems, control actions, influence the environment, have confidence in one's abilities, respect oneself, and achieve satisfaction in one's own efforts. If children are not trained to be independent from an early age, they will depend on others even when they grow up. Children who are not independent are caused by abilities that have not been mastered at a certain age and the influence of parents. Factors that influence learning independence are social sources such as parents, family members, and teachers, as well as skills that provide opportunities to train students' learning independence. Students' learning independence can be increased with the motivation provided by teachers, parents and students themselves. The role of parents is important in shaping a child's personality and social abilities. The responsibility and role of parents is very important in developing socially adaptive behavior in children with mental retardation. For this reason, parents need to know effective ways to educate and shape children's independence so that their intellectual potential can develop well and be able to face life realistically and objectively. Parental support is important in children's development in various aspects, including academics, self-concept, self-esteem, self-confidence, motivation, and mental health. The role of parents influences children's achievement, emotions, and school adjustment. The problem is that the role of parents is less effective. The formation of children's self-confidence cannot be separated from the role of parents and family who provide a sense of security and acceptance. Family is a close place for children to be open in dealing with problems. Observations and interviews show that the level of independence of children at the Gugus Cempaka Kindergarten varies. T safe The Cempaka Cluster of Central Banjarmasin children have children who are less independent. There are those who still rely on their parents at school, always have help in doing assignments, are not confident during marching activities, and are afraid to appear in front of the class. This research has the title "The Influence of Parental Roles on Children's Social Independence in Taman "K children of the Cempaka Cluster, Central Banjarmasin District" .

METHODS

Description of Research Location

Based on the research results, it shows that the level of characteristics of the respondents shows that the kindergarten used as a place for this research is in T safe The K children of the Cempaka Cluster, Central Banjarmasin District,

namely the Dhammasoka Integrated Preschool, the Mother's Love Integrated Preschool, the Group Learning Khalifah Banjarmasin 2 , Integrated Early Childhood Education Joyce , Taman K children . _ Love Ananda, K group Learning Abdhu S allam, Paud Mirzam, Paud Terpadu Aisyiah 2, Paud Terpadu Negeri Pembina , Taman K children _ Islam Sabilal Muhtadin, Taman K children _ Hippindo Foundation, T four Custody _ A Mawaddah's son , T is safe K children _ At-Tibyan, T safe K children _ Al Kautsar and T are safe K children _ Aisyiyah 18. Central Banjarmasin District consists of 12 sub-districts, including: Teluk Dalam Subdistrict, Mawar Subdistrict, Kertak Baru Ilir Subdistrict, Kertak Baru Ulu Subdistrict, Pasar Lama Subdistrict, Seberang Mesjid Subdistrict, Melayu Subdistrict, Gadang Subdistrict, Pekapuran Laut Subdistrict, Subdistrict Sungai Baru, Kelayan Luar Subdistrict and Antasan Besar Subdistrict .

Banjarmasin City, South Kalimantan , Basirih Subdistrict is the subdistrict that has the largest area in West Banjarmasin District among 9 other subdistricts with an area of 3.65 km², or covering around 27.30% of the total area of West Banjarmasin Subdistrict. Meanwhile, the Telawang sub-district area has the smallest area with an area of 0.57 km² or around 4.26 of the area.

The regional boundaries of Central Banjarmasin sub-district are as follows:

1. Borders with North Banjarmasin District
2. Borders with East Banjarmasin District
3. Borders with South Banjarmasin District
4. Borders with West Banjarmasin District

Research Participants

Population

The characteristics of the population in this study are children who are in group B and they still lack social independence, especially in terms of socializing and interacting with their friends and their inability to understand other people and they are still poor at communicating with other people.

In this study, the population was parents of children in the Gugus Cempaka Kindergarten, Central Banjarmasin District. The accessible population in this study can be seen in the following table:

Table 1 (Research Population)

No	School name	N amount
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No	School name	N amount
1.	Dhammasoka Integrated Preschool	28
2.	Mother's Love Integrated Preschool	26
3.	KB Caliph Bjm 2	28
4.	Joyce Integrated Preschool	32
5.	TK. Cinta Ananda	26
6.	KB Abdhu Sallam	20
7.	Miriam's preschool	20
8.	Aisyiah Integrated Preschool 2	20
9.	Pembina State Integrated Preschool	20
10.	Tk. Islam Sabilal Muhtadin	36
11.	Nature Kindergarten Based on Character Dear Mother	24
12.	KB. Mawaddah	22
13.	Kindergarten At-Tibyan	24
14.	Tk. Al Kautsar	16
15.	Kindergarten Aisyiyah 18	18
Amount		360

So the sample size for this study is 360 parents of children who will be given questionnaires during this research.

Sample

The sample size in this study was determined using the Slovin formula and a significance level of 5% from a population of 189 parents of children in the Gugus Cempaka Kindergarten, Central Banjarmasin District.

Determining the size of the quantity uses the Slovin formula as follows:

$$N = \frac{n}{1+n(d)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size

d = desired level of confidence (5%)

For this reason, the number of samples for this research is:

$$N = \frac{360}{1 + 360(0.05)^2} = \frac{360}{1.9} = 189,4$$

The sampling technique used in this research was to determine the sample for each school, the researcher used cluster sampling is a group random sample where the population does not consist of individuals, but rather consists of groups of individuals or clusters . Regional sampling techniques are used to determine samples if the object to be studied or data source is very broad.

Sugiyono (2010:90), namely: After the population is calculated using the formula above, it can be depicted in the table below:

Table 2 (Research Sample)

No	School name	Sample
1	Joyce Integrated Preschool	20
2	Kindergarten At-Tibyan	16
3	Kindergarten Mawaddah	21
4	Tk. Islam Sabilal Muhtadin	21
5	Pembina State Integrated Preschool	16
6	Kindergarten Kartika V-23	16
7	Kindergarten Aisyiyah Bustanul Athfal 30	21
8	Kindergarten Character Based Nature	21
9	Kindergarten Jami Mosque Islam	16
10	Kindergarten Kemala Bhayangkari 04	21

No	School name	Sample
	Amount	189

So the sample for this study consisted of 189 parents of children who attended these 10 schools.

Sampling Method

Regarding the aim of this research, in determining the research sample, first determine the sampling method. Sampling is carried out on sampling units, where the sampling unit consists of one group (cluster). Each item (individual) in the selected group will be taken as a sample. This method is used: if the population can be divided into groups and every characteristic studied is present in each group.

This method is used: if the population can be divided into groups and every characteristic studied is present in each group. Judging from the description of the characteristics of the kindergartens studied in Central Banjarmasin District.

Randomly select one of the levels (eg level II). So the parents of all kindergarten children who were at level II were taken as samples (Cluster). Advantages: Does not require a population list. Less transportation costs Disadvantages: Difficult estimation procedure (Sugiyono 2014:82).

Research Design

This type of research uses quantitative descriptive research. The method used in this research is a descriptive method with associative (correlational) techniques. Sugiyono (2011:89) defines associative research as research that aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables. A similar opinion according to Arikunto (2010:247) states that research using correlation techniques (correlational research) tries to determine how strong the relationship between variables is.

Research variable

There are two types of variables in this research, namely independent variables or independent variables and dependent variables or dependent variables.

1. Independent (free) variable, namely the variable that influences or is the cause of changes or emergence of other variables, in this case the dependent variable. The independent variable in this research is the Role of Parents (X).
2. Dependent (bound) variable, namely the variable that is influenced or is the result, due to the presence of other variables, which are then called independent variables. In this research the dependent variable is Social Independence (Y).

Data collection technique

The general data used in this research is quantitative. The data in question is a series of numbers that describe the variables in this research. Thus, the data collection technique in this research was carried out using a

questionnaire. A questionnaire is a data collection technique through a form containing questions or statements to obtain the expected information from respondents. The technique for using data using a questionnaire, the basic considerations are: a) So that the measurement results of the variables studied can be analyzed statistically; b) The data collection tool obtains objective data; c) This data collection tool allows research to be carried out easily and can save time, costs and energy.

This research uses a questionnaire or questionnaire or attitude scale as an instrument for collecting data. The questionnaire was distributed to all parents of children at the Cempaka Cluster Kindergarten, Central Banjarmasin with several question options in the form of an attitude scale. The questionnaire is prepared based on variables that have been determined and developed into indicators.

For the purposes of this research, the questionnaire/questionnaire in the form of a Likert scale was first tested before being used. Testing the instrument was the first stage in the research data collection process. Instrument testing is intended to obtain an instrument that has validity and reliability in accordance with applicable regulations. Instrument testing was carried out in two stages, namely the first stage asking educational management experts (expert judgment) about the construction which is described into variables, sub-variables and their indicators, as well as improving the grammar to make it more operational.

In the second stage, the test instrument was given to the parents of children who were not included in the research sample. This instrument was tested on parents of children outside the research sample by taking 30 parents of children. In this research, there are four instruments that will be tested, namely (1) the variable instrument for parenting patterns, (2) the instrument for the social independence variable.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

Respondent Characteristics

Based on the results of the characteristics of respondents from parents of children, totaling 189 people in terms of parents' education level, parents' age, and parents' work which is related to parental role issues carried out at home. So it can be seen in the following description:

Table 3 (Respondent Characteristics)

No	Parental education level	F	%
1	Elementary/Kindergarten	19	10.1
2	SMP/SMA/MA/SMK	150	79.4
3	College	20	10.6
Amount		189	100.0
No	Parental Age	F	%
1	21-30	38	20.1

2	31-40	126	66.7
3	40-50	25	13.2
Amount		189	100
No	Parents' job	F	%
1	Laborer	21	11.1
2	Private (trader/contractor/labourer)	132	69.8
3	Civil servants (TNI/Teachers/Polri)	36	19
Amount		189	100

Based on the results of the parents' educational characteristics, most of them graduated from SMPN/SMA, 15 people, 79.4%. This shows that the level of education still has an influence on children, seen from the ability of parents to provide education to their children, especially in making children independent in learning.

The table of age levels of respondent parents who send their children to school in this cluster is that most of them are 31-40 years old, totaling 126 people (66.7%). This shows that they are still at a productive age and are still able to provide direction and guidance within the family.

The results of the parent's employment level were that the highest was private (trader/contractor/labourer) amounting to 132 people (69.8%). This shows that they are more busy outside earning a living than at home, so they still pay less attention to their children, especially in monitoring their behavior.

Descriptive Research Results

The role of parents

Based on the results of the role of parents, it can be seen from the following

**Table 4 (Frequency Distribution of Parental Roles)
Descriptive Statistics**

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
The role of parents	189	34.00	56.00	48.1270	5.86050
Valid N (listwise)	189				

The results of the level of assessment of the role of parents can be seen from high, medium and low levels of parental role which can be described in the research results, namely 14 items x 4 = 56 highest scores and 14 items x 1 = 14 lowest scores. The categorization of parental role variables is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ideal mean (Mi)} &= \frac{1}{2} (\text{max score } i + \text{min score } i) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} (56+14) \\ \text{Mi} &= 35 \\ \text{Ideal standard deviation (SDi)} &= \frac{1}{6} (\text{max score } i - \text{min score } i) \\ &= \frac{1}{6} (56-14) \\ \text{SDi} &= 7 \end{aligned}$$

- Low Group = $X \leq (Mi - 1SDi)$
 = $X \leq (35 - 7)$
 = $X \leq 28$
- Medium Group = $(Mi - 1SDi) < X < (Mi + 1SDi)$
 = $(35 + 7) < X < (35 - 7)$
 = $(42) < X < (28)$
- High Group = $X \geq (Mi + 1.SDi)$
 = $X \geq (35 + 7)$
 = $X \geq (42)$

Based on the results of the identification table, the results of the parental role categories can be made as follows:

Table 5 (Results of Parental Role Categories)

No	Intervals	F	%	Category
1.	$X \leq 28$	0	0	Low
2.	$(42) < X < (28)$	11	5.8	Currently
3.	$> (42)$	178	94.2	Tall
Amount		189	100	

The results of the categorization of the role of parents while supervising children are included in the high category of parental role totaling 178 people (94.2%), then the role of parents included in the medium category is 11 people (5.8%), and the role of parents included in the low category is 0 people (0%). So these results can be seen in the following graph:

Graph 1 (Role of parents)

This means that the role of parents so far is still relatively high at 178 people (94.2%), the role of parents is good and still good in guiding children. Based on the table above, it can be categorized that the role of parents so far is still relatively good in providing protection to children when at home or when hanging out with friends in the child's social environment.

Children's Social Independence

The results of research on children's independence in everyday life show that

Table 6 (Distribution of children's social independence)

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Independence	189	76.00	112.00	95.8836	8.85685
Valid N (listwise)	189				

The results of the level of assessment of the child's independence can be seen from high, medium and low independence which can be described in the research results of 29 items $\times$ 4 = 116 highest scores and 29 items $\times$ 1 = 29 lowest scores. The categorization of children's independence variables is as follows:

$$\text{Ideal mean (Mi)} = \frac{1}{2} (\text{max score } i + \text{min score } i)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} (116+29)$$

$$\text{Mi} = 72.5$$

$$\text{Ideal standard deviation (SDi)} = \frac{1}{6} (\text{max score } i - \text{min score } i)$$

$$= \frac{1}{6} (116-29)$$

$$\text{SDi} = 14.5$$

$$\text{Low Group} = X \leq (\text{Mi} - 1\text{SDi})$$

$$= X \leq (72.5 - 14.5)$$

$$= X \leq 58$$

$$\text{Medium Group} = (\text{Mi} - 1\text{SDi}) < X < (\text{Mi} + 1\text{SDi})$$

$$= (72.5 - 14.5) < X < (72.5 + 14.5)$$

$$= (58) < X < (87)$$

$$\text{High Group} = X \geq (\text{Mi} + 1\text{SDi})$$

$$= X \geq (72.5 + 14.5)$$

$$= X \geq (87)$$

Based on the results of the identification table, the results of the child's independence category can be made as follows:

Table 7 (Results of children's social independence categories)

No	Intervals	F	%	Category
1.	$X \leq 58$	0	0	Low
2.	$(58) \leq X \leq (87)$	31	16.4	Currently
3.	$X \geq (87)$	158	83.6	Tall
Amount		189	100	

This means that the social independence of children who are classified as high is 158 people, namely (83.6%), then the independence of children who are classified as moderate is 31 people (16.4%) and those who are classified as low are none. Based on the table above, it can be categorized that children's independence is still considered good or independent.

The results of these percentages can be seen from the following diagram:

Graph 2 (Children's independence)

This shows that children's independence is included in the high category, namely 83.6%. Children's independence is very important in providing good things to children, especially in providing understanding for children to learn to understand their own character both at home and at school.

Children's independence in various things is very important, one of which is in learning. Children who are independent in their learning will be able to better understand the tasks given to them by school. They will reduce themselves from depending on others so as to make themselves able to carry out the tasks required of them.

Discussion

A child's social independence in behaving in everyday life depends on how parents provide education to their children at home. Children who are less independent in their lives could be due to the lack of role of people at home in supervising and providing good education in learning and behaving towards others. Parents, as the main educators for their children, are a child's main role model whose behavior will be imitated and followed. Giving birth, nurturing and educating children well is to realize the benefit of religion and the world and the hereafter. More than that, the existence of children is a lifeline for parents after they die, in the form of a reward for good deeds. Also maintaining their good name and inheriting their inheritance (Jalaluddin. 2015: 204).

In educating their children, the role of parents is very necessary, to provide provisions for life for the child. The flow of empiricism with the famous figure John Locke (1632-1704) and his famous doctrine is "tabula rasa", a Latin term which means a blank notebook or blank sheet. The role of parents in making children more independent in thinking and able to be socially independent will enable them to carry out the tasks given by their parents or teachers at school.

The values contained in the role of parents are the role of parents towards their children, including, first, educating them well, which is meant regarding health from birth to adulthood, whether in the form of choosing a food menu, medication, or other preventive measures. Also by tempering their bodies with wholesome exercise and upright conduct. Second, breastfeeding,

breastfeeding a baby is a sharia obligation for both parents. This is at a sufficient time for the growth of flesh and bone strength. Third, shave their heads in the first week of birth. It is sunnah to shave the heads of babies, both male and female, on the seventh day of birth and give alms equal to the weight of their hair in silver scales to the poor. Fourth, educating their morals. What is meant by moral development is educating children to love things that are noble and high, and to hate things that are low.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

There is an influence of the role of parents on the social independence of children in Taman K children of the Cempaka Cluster, Central Banjarmasin District. The role of parents as educators in activities at home has a 15% influence on the social independence of children in Taman K children of the Cempaka Cluster, Central Banjarmasin District, while 85% are influenced by other factors.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions from the research results, the researcher proposed several suggestions to various parties interested in the results of this research, including:

1. Schools should pay more attention to children's social independence by giving freedom to teachers in developing children's abilities in interacting with children by discussing or asking questions.
2. For parents to pay more attention and observe their children's social behavior at home and not pressure their children according to their parents' wishes, this can make their children capable and more independent in socializing in their daily lives.
3. For future researchers, as input in understanding the variable role of parents in children's social independence in the Gugus Cempaka Kindergarten, Central Banjarmasin District, apart from these variables, other variables can be studied.

FURTHER STUDY

With research limited to variables, researchers recommends that similar research be conducted targeting different variables different groups or contexts. As a result, adding mediating variables can. It can also be studied by future researchers to gain new insight into this matter relationship between variables. The results of this research can help future researchers identify what improvements the company can make in order to improve their operations to be more sustainable and able to face change. The recommendations above will help researchers to identify what factors have a significant influence.

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